

Social Media in Education: Assessing the Effectiveness of Facebook Use in Developing English Writing Skill of the Students of English Department of Dhaka College and Eden College

Mst. Ummehani Akter, Lecturer, Department of English, Dhaka College, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract: The study focuses on the effectiveness of Facebook in improving the English writing skills of the students of the English department of Dhaka College and Eden College, two prominent government colleges in Bangladesh. Though the primary aim of students' Facebook use is entertainment, the research suggests Facebook as an educational tool. This study collects data through a survey questionnaire via a Google form addressing qualitative and quantitative questions. Data is collected purposively from 323 undergraduate students of the English department in these two colleges, where 161 are male, and 162 are female, population size is about 2000. The result of this research emphasizes that Facebook can be an effective platform to develop students' writing skills by providing lots of opportunities for practicing and receiving feedback. However, the contribution can face challenges such as frequent distraction, lack of structured guidelines, and limitation of adequate logistic support. The study concludes with recommendations for maximizing the utility of Facebook as an educational tool with some limitations. This study focuses on a specific issue (writing) in a particular department (English) of the two government colleges in Bangladesh, which is a limitation of the study and leaves scope for future research regarding the usefulness of Facebook use in improving English language skills.

General statement: This Study focuses the function of Facebook as an educational tool for enhancing English writing skills of the students of English Department of Dhaka College and Eden College.

Objective: The aim of the paper is 'To assess the effectiveness of Facebook in developing the English writing skills of the undergraduate students of English department in Dhaka College and Eden College, two prominent government colleges in Bangladesh.'

Methodology: Data were collected through a survey questionnaire of Google Forms, concluding both qualitative and quantitative questions. A purposive sample of 323 undergraduate students (161 male and 162 female) were surveyed from a population of approximate 2000.

Purposive significant result: The result suggests that Facebook can be an effective platform for developing English Writing skill of the learners by providing opportunities for practicing and receiving feedback.

Implication of the study: The study implies that integration of Facebook in education can be fruitful by serving a platform for purposeful aim to improve writing skills. Though the challenges like distraction, lack of logistic support must be addressed.

Limitation and further recommendation: This study's focus only on a single language skill among the four skills, writing in a particular department (English) at two government colleges is a limitation. Future researchers can explore the feasibility of the study in broader area covering the whole country and also the other language skills, reading, writing and listening.

Key word: Facebook, English writing, two government colleges under the 7 affiliated colleges of Bangladesh,

1. Introduction:

In this modern era of technological advancement, integration of social media into education has become popular worldwide as it offers a tremendous opportunity of developing learning experiences. Facebook, Youtube, Intragram, Whatsapp are some leading social media used for educational purposes (S. Patmanthara, 2019).

Among them, Facebook is one of the most used social media utilized by the students both for personal and academic purposes all over the world.

The students of Bangladesh are no exception. Though, the students' primary aim of using Facebook is entertainment but gradually, it could be used as an educational platform for improving English language skills, specially, English writing skill (Sufian, 2015). It is noteworthy, that when Bangladeshi students use English alphabets for Facebook writing either for a status, comment or even in private chat. However, using English letters does not always ensure that they are using English language. Sometimes, they use English alphabets to write Bangla words, popularly known as 'Banglish' (Bangla+English) (Islam F. S., 2018).

This study aims to explore whether using Facebook is developing students' English language learning skills, specially writing skills, or if it is leading them to a practice of blundering languages decreasing their learnt knowledge. This is a qualitative study, collecting data from 323 undergraduate students majoring English literature and language from two government colleges, Dhaka College and Eden College, affiliated with Dhaka University. These two colleges are the most prominent government colleges in Bangladesh among them Dhaka college is a boys college and Eden College is a female college. The reason behind this selection aims to examine any gender influence on the use of English in social media.

The main aim of this study is to determine the extent to which Facebook helps English Department students to develop their English language proficiency focusing on writing skill.

1. How does Facebook usage contribute in achieving English writing proficiency?
2. What measure can be taken to make face-booking useful in terms of learning English?

Rationale of the Study:

The daily use of social media has transformed peoples' way of communication, mood of learning and sharing information. Among these platforms, Facebook is very popular among the young generation, particularly students, who frequently use Facebook as a tool of entertainment, concept-sharing and for virtual communication (Sayeed, 2020). However, it has potential as an educational tool which can contribute in English language learning in the context of higher education in Bangladesh.

This study focuses on the effectiveness of Facebook in developing the English writing skills of the students of English department of Dhaka College and Eden College. These two colleges are the leading colleges among the government colleges of Bangladesh. After studying English as an compulsory subject for 12 years from class 1 to class 12 (2020) and getting admission in English department, these students are facing difficulties in communicating successfully in English, specially flawless English writing, which is a mandatory skill for academic success and global competition.

The rationale of this study is to find out an alternative effective method to support students enhancing their language learning proficiency. Traditional classroom always cannot provide a student enough opportunities for practicing and improving his writing skill because of several barriers like class size, time bound and syllabus (Rahman, 2018). On the contrary, a social media platform like Facebook, a student enjoys an unlimited access to write, share and receive feedback on his posts and comments and private chats in English.

This paper, by selecting these two colleges will try to access the effectiveness of Facebook as a supplement of educational equipment in enhancing English writing skills of the students (Alam, 2019). The finding suggests the challenges followed by recommendation for achieving better result of using Facebook as an educational platform for language skills development.

Moreover, as English is a must for academic and professional success, particularly for a global citizen, this study aims to contribute in multimodal approaches in teaching English by suggesting Facebook as an effective mode of it focusing on the digital habit of today's students. The outcome of the study may suggest for a broader application of social media in education for improving learning experience and effectiveness.

Literature review:

A good number of studies have already been done on the impact of Facebook upon the Facebook in English language learning. Most of these researches have shown that the controlled use of Facebook has a positive impact on the improvement of language skills.

Ibrahim (2013) to examine the effect of Facebook in English language learning specially improving English writing skill implies an experiment on the students of ninth grade in the Latin Patriarchate Private School in Qabatia District in Zababdeh, where the researcher has shown that the experimental group who were taught effective writing by using technological tools basically Facebook had done much better than the controlled group who were taught traditionally in the post test examination. This finding of the paper can be concluded by saying Facebook has a positive influence in enhancing English writing skill. Almost a similar study was done on the undergraduate students at Chiang Mai Rajahat University, Thailand, where a Facebook group was used as the instrument. The students were assigned to do day to day communication in English in that group. That study also found that Facebook could motivate the students to communicate in English (Srirat, 2014).

Likewise, a Facebook group was observed by (Kasuma, Four characteristics of Facebook activities for English language learning: A study of Malaysian university students' needs and preferences., 2017) where the students participated in a Basic English Proficiency (BEP) course in a university situated at the northern part of Malaysia. The students were asked to do some activities like discussion and creating English learning content. The result of the research is the students are in need of technological help in learning but that should be under teachers' supervision. Another study was done in the context of Malaysia, where the researcher found that using Facebook helps students in learning new vocabulary and sentence structure (Kasuma, 2017).

In a study some Turkish students were provided some Facebook games, where the researchers' finding was the playing Facebook game can increase students' English vocabulary (Güvendir, 2015). At the same time some students have confident that Facebook can be a learning app if they communicate there only in English in a collaborative way and this would develop their English writing skills (Jassim, 2019). As a whole, students believe that Facebook can be used to encourage and facilitates their English language learning (AbuSa'aleek, 2015).

But this could not be generalized. Facebook can be an effective tool providing English language and literature related knowledge (Salameh, 2017). Facebook can be a fruitful learning tool for community practice to improve self-respect and confidence (Kabilan, 2016). Students can enrich their English knowledge with new words and grammar rules from their Facebook using (Faryadi, 2017). In that regard, some students feel that the learning outcome using FB can be better if they know each other (Alam, Facebook as a Formal Instructional Environment in Facilitating L2 Writing: Impacts and Challenges., 2019). It could be a good network for sharing materials and resources (Chowdhury, 2021).

The university level students in Bangladesh also prefer to use English in giving Facebook status because they consider it as a prestigious issue (Biswas, 2022). Again, the tertiary level students intend to use English while using Facebook (Biswas, 2022). However, the laxative knowledge of some of the students may be inadequate for using English in Facebook (Islam F. S., Facebook and Students' Sub-Standard English: A Context of Bangladesh., 2018). From the previous works, it could be said in a nut shell that, Facebook could bring a revolutionary change in English writing standard, especially for the discussed students of English department of the two colleges under proper guideline.

Research Gap:

The use of social media like Facebook in improving English writing skills has not been explored widely by the students of Bangladesh. Although several studies have weighted the role of social networking site in language learning, there is a demand of focused researched on the role of Facebook as an effective platform for academic practice to improve specific language skills, specially writing.

Moreover, existing researches often focus on the broader aspects of social media usage in education, like student engagement, collaboration, and communication. However, the potential of Facebook to serve as a tool for improving language skills among the third world countries like Bangladesh has not been addressed adequately. This is particularly true for the students of Dhaka College and Eden College, where students are actively seeking ways to develop their English proficiency for academic and professional purposes.

Additionally, while some studies have examined the use of social media in education in western contexts, there is a significant gap in understanding the cultural and educational gap for Bangladeshi students. The unique challenges and opportunities experienced by the local context, including students' digital literacy, access to technology, and language learning requires more targeted investigation.

This study aims to fill these gaps by providing evidence on the effectiveness of Facebook in improving English writing skills of the students of English Departments of Dhaka College and Eden College. By focusing on a specific skills and context, this research seeks to contribute to more utilization of Facebook as an educational tool in diverse cultural settings.

Regarding the impact of Facebook in enhancing English language proficiency among the student of Bangladesh a good number of researches have already been done. Most of these studies were based on the private university students. Impact of Facebook using on the government college English department of Bangladesh has not been done yet. This study would try to find out the impact of Facebook in improving English language proficiency among the students of English department of two renowned government colleges in Dhaka city among them one is female college.

Methodology:

This is a mixed method research. The researcher used questionnaire to collect data in purposive sampling method. The questionnaire is served to the participants as a Google form. The questionnaire was divided in four section containing 22 questions focusing on the students' use of English in Facebook for developing their English writing skills. The respondent group had submitted their answer in Google platform. All together twenty questions were asked. The total respondents are 323 among the respondents 161 were male and 162 were female student. All of them were from two renowned colleges of Dhaka city affiliated with Dhaka University. The questions were open-ended and close-ended. It took around 5 minutes to fill the Google form.

Sampling: The participants were selected purposively to meet the design of the study. The number of respondents from each colleges and each education level from Honours' first year to Honours' fourth year were almost equal to get the answer whether gender and level of study has any impact on the use of Facebook for improving English writing skills or not.

Data analysis: Among the 22 questions three questions were qualitative and other 19 questions were quantitative. Quantitative data were analyzed by SPSS and the qualitative data separated according to the headings and were measured by tally and then the tally and the responses were presented in SPSS.

Data Presentation, analysis and findings:

The Analysis of Data, discussion and findings:

Demographical information analysis:

A survey questionnaire was served to the 323 respondents of these two colleges English department. The questionnaire contains 22 questions all together. The questions were set to interrogate if the students' use of English in Facebook has any impact in their English communication skills and what instigates them to use English in Facebook. There are also some questions to explore the relation of the students' gender, level of

education and parents' education, and the students' home town has any relation to their use of English in Facebook for educational purposes.

Number of students	323
Male (students from Dhaka College)	161
Female (students from Eden College)	162
Level of Education (Students')	80 students are from Honours' 1 st year, 81 from Honours' 2 nd year, 81 from Honours' 3 rd year and 81 students are from Honours' 4 th year.
Home Town	202 students are from different villages of Bangladesh, 46 are from suburban and 75 students are from town. Among 75 students from town 68 are from Dhaka and the other 07 students are from the other town of Bangladesh.
Parents education level	80 parents of 323 students have completed SSC level, 63 HSC, 43 HA, 44 MA and other 93 parents are below SSC level.
The highest educated person in your family	In case of 77 students is father, 21 is mother, 47 is brother, 37 is sister and 141 are the students themselves.

Table 1: Students' Profile

The data provides insights into the demographics and educational backgrounds of 323 students. The male students are 49.80% and the female students are 50.20%. The students were selected purposively to examine that if the gender issue effects educational use of Facebook or not. The distribution across all four years of Honours study is nearly uniform, with minimal variation, suggesting an even spread of students across the educational levels.

The parents of the students are from various educational backgrounds. 93 out of 323 have below SSC level. The students themselves are the highest educated of their family and the amount is 141 out of 323. It also shows the positive opportunities for both male and female students. The majority of the students are from villages and the number is 202 out of 323. The data suggests a trend of increasing educational attainment among the young generation, especially from rural areas, with many becoming the first in their families to pursue higher education.

The question number 01 and 02 are about the basic information about the students' institution name and current level of study. Question 3 to 6, are designed to focus on the students home town and their parents' education and the highest educated person in their family.

Findings 1: This general information indicates that the most of the students are from villages. 202 students are from villages including villages of Dhaka, Narayangonj, Chittagonj districts. Only 75 students are from different towns. About the parents' education level only 87 parents have completed their bachelor and Masters' degree. In 141 cases, the students are the highest educated in their family.

General information about Facebook use analysis:

The next questions from 7 to 12 are about the general information of the students' use of Facebook. These questions tries to examine how many of the 323 students use Facebook for educational purposes and for how long they have been using Facebook and when did they have created an account in Facebook.

When did you create a Facebook account	155 students opened an account with Facebook before SSC, 57 during SSC, 58 during HSC, 53 after HSC
How often do you use Facebook	289 students use Facebook daily, 19 students use it weekly, 7 students use it rarely, 7 students never use it, 1 student prefers not to answer.
How many hours do you spend in Facebook	Among the 289 students who use Facebook daily, 50 students use Facebook less than 1 hour, 87 students use it from 1-2 hours, 95 students use it from 2-3 hours, 57 use Facebook more than 3 hours.
Do you use Facebook for educational purpose	277 students including the regular user and the rarely user (total 315) use Facebook for educational purposes and the other 38 students use Facebook only for entertainment
How often do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing	192 students (among 277) use Facebook daily for educational purposes, 57 use weekly, 15 use monthly, 13 use it rarely
How often do you use Facebook for educational purposes focusing on English writing daily	Among the 192 students of regular user 90 use it for 30 minute to 1 hour, 63 for 1-2 hour and 39 for less than 30 minute.

Table 2: Facebook account opening and use for education focusing on English writing.

The table shows that most of the students (48%) created Facebook account before SSC and 90% of the students use Facebook daily, indicating both social and academic purposes. 47 % of the students spent 2 hour in Facebook. 86% of the students use Facebook for educational purposes, including both regular and rare users. The students are engaging in Facebook for academic content, likely study groups, online resources and peer collaboration. Among the 277 students who use Facebook for education, 69% (192) use it daily for academic work, showing its utility as a learning tool. Weekly and monthly users refer to it for specific academic needs. 192 students demand that they use Facebook daily for educational work, spend between 30 minutes to 2 hours. This suggests that Facebook can be a supporting element for traditional educational activities.

These data indicates that they students are engage in Facebook form very young age. Facebook is included in their daily activities and they spend a very good amount of time on Facebook daily. Thought the students demand that they use Facebook for educational purposes but they amount is not significant. Students use Facebook as a supporting platform of their formal classes.

The data shows that the most of the students has created a Facebook account before their SSC in junior level from between class 6 to 8. The students are using to use Facebook daily and they use it for educational purpose on regular basis. Among the students who use Facebook for regular basis, 90 among 192 students use Facebook for 30 minute to 1 hour regularly and, 63 students use it for 1-2 hour and 39 use it for educational purposes for less than 30 minutes.

Findings 2: The finding of this part is the students are using Facebook from a tender age. Students are involved in following educational groups, and several activities as a supportive for formal classes. However, the duration of Facebook use is not significant, only 63 among 192 daily FB user for educational purpose spent time for 1 to 2 hours.

Use of English writing in Facebook related questions analysis:

The next section is about the students' use of English in Facebook. From question 13 to is about the use of English and the motivations behind using English in Facebook, the benefits and challenges and the recommendations of the students in using English in a Facebook

Do you use English in Facebook	315 students use English in Facebook including those who Facebook for entertainment. The rest 7 students do not use Facebook rarely or never. So they did not answer this question.
What motivates you to use English in Facebook (Select all those apply)	50 students use English as it increases their prestige, 140 students use it as it helps them to make new foreign friends, 106 students use English as it helps them to obtain a good marks in exam, 112 students' writing skills has been developed.
Have you participated in any English writing activities or groups on Facebook	171 students out of 315 are engage in English writing practice group. Other 144 students are practicing English through chatting and comments.
If yes, what kind of activities or groups (answer all those apply)	113 students are engage in several writing groups, 134 are the member of different English learning pages, 213 students are engage in writing challenges groups and 144 students depend on peer review and feedbacks. Students are engage in more than one group here.
Do you believe that participating in these activities or groups has improved your English writing skills	All 315 students have a strong believe that these Facebook activities are enhancing their English writing skills.
How has Facebook helped you to improve your English writing (answer all those apply)	All 315 students have a strong believe that these Facebook activities are enhancing their English writing skills though 51 students use Facebook not for educational purpose. 76 students are satisfied with the resources and materials, 83 are benefited by the peer review and feedbacks. 79 believe that Facebook is a greater exposure to different writing style to them. Students are engage in more than one group here.
Which specific areas of your English writing have been improved through the use of Facebook (answer all those apply)	70 students agree that their knowledge related to grammar has been improved. Other 93 students admit that their vocabulary has been enriched, 49 students have improved their sentence structure, 57 students agree that their sentence coherence and cohesion has improved and 53 students' creativity and originality has been improved. Students are engage in more than one group here.
What challenges have you faced when using Facebook for improving English writing (answer all those apply)	All 323 students answered this answer. Among these students 57 students face the problem of distraction, 56 feel that Facebook lacks structural materials, 49 feedback is inconsistent, 70 privacy concern , 141 students lack sufficient vocabulary and 34 lacks confidence. Students have response to more than one option.
Are you satisfied in using Facebook as an English writing platform	A linkert scale is used here to measure the level of satisfaction with Facebook as an English writing platform. 58 students are very satisfied, 130 are satisfied, 100 remain neutral, 25 are dissatisfied and 1 is strongly dissatisfied.
Would you recommend using Facebook for improving English writing to others	238 students would recommend Facebook as English writing platform to others 85 students would not recommend it.
Recommendation	Recommend monitoring for the better application of Facebook, making more foreign friend, to engage in more practice group.

Table 3: Facebook as an English writing skills development platform

The table shows the students use of Facebook as a platform of improving English writing skills among the students of Dhaka College and Eden College. 315 students use English on Facebook, including those using it for entertainment. Almost all students use English on Facebook, indicating a widespread integration of English into their social media habits, possibly driven by academic and social motivations. The most motivations are developing foreign friendships (44%), 33% of the students has agreed that after using Facebook as English writing platform they have got good marks, and improving writing skills (35.6%), indicating that English is seen as a tool for both social and academic advancement.

More than half (171) of the students actively participate in structured English writing groups, while others use informal means (chatting, comment) to practice English. This shows diverse approaches to improving writing skills through the platform. A significant number of students engage learning pages and groups, indicating that these pages offer valuable resources and community support. Peer review and feedback also play a role in learning.

Findings 3: The general believe is the benefits of using Facebook for improving English suggests that the platform is perceived as a practical and helpful tool for language development. Students highlights the importance of Facebook’s resources, peer reviews, and exposure to varied writing styles, showing that the platform offers a broad range of benefits for language learning. Vocabulary development and grammar are the two area that most students report improving.

These findings suggest that Facebook is a valuable tool for enhancing both foundational language skills and creative writing. The primary challenges are vocabulary limitations and privacy concern, while other cited distractions and the platform’s lack of formal learning structures. Those obstacles suggest a need for more focused language support. Most students are satisfied or very satisfied with Facebook as a writing platform. However, a significant portion (100 students) remains neutral, indicating room for improvement. Almost 74% of the students recommend Facebook use for improving writing, suggesting that despite its challenges, most students see it as a beneficial tool (Alam, 2019). These recommendations focus on maximizing the educational potential of Facebook by increasing structured engagement and expanding social networks for language practice.

Cross table analysis:

The research tried to set up the relations between education level and use of Facebook for educational purposes targeting the development of English writing skills. It also checked the name of college and use of English during using Facebook for improving English writing. This college name and English use in Facebook is asked as the these two colleges indicate the male and female as Eden College is a female college and Dhaka College is a male college. Next question determined to explore the influence of family education on a students’ use of English in Facebook for enhancing English writing skills.

Do you use Facebook for educational purpose?

Education Level		Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing?		
		Yes	No	Total
Education Level	Honours 1st year	68	10	78 (other 2 students rarely use Fb)
	Honours 2nd year	58	21	79 (other 3 students rarely use Fb)

	Honours 3rd year	74	6	80 (other 1 students rarely use Fb)
	Honours 4th year	70	8	78 (other 2 students rarely use Fb)
Total		270	45	315

Table 4: Relation between Facebook use for developing Writing skills and level of education.

This table shows that among the 78 students of Honours' 1st year 68 use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing skills improvement, and among the 79 students of Honours' 2nd year 58 use Facebook for educational purpose specially for developing English writing proficiency, 74 students of 3rd year use it for educational purpose based on the same writing skills and 70 Honours' 4th year students use Facebook for educational purpose emphasizing writing skills.

Findings 4: This statistic shows that the use of Facebook among the students for educational purpose increases among the students of 3rd and 4th year, who are close to the end of their graduation. It is a little less in 2nd year but when the students get admission in Honours' 1st year, they take interest in learning something from Facebook, that is the reason of their higher number of uses for educational purposes to sharpen their writing skills. The other students use Facebook rarely, so they are not included in the table.

Name of your institution * Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing Cross tabulation

Name of Institution		Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing?		
		Yes	No	Total
Name of Institution	Dhaka College	137	22	159
	Eden College	140	16	156
Total		277	38	315

Table-5: Use of Facebook for English writing among male and female student.

This table shows that the gender has almost no impact on students' use of Facebook for educational purposes. Among the 182 female students of Eden College 140 use it for educational purpose, percentage is 78% and 16 do not use it for education. On the other hand among the 181 male students of Dhaka College, 137 students use it for education, percentage is 75% and other 22 does not use it for education.

Findings 5: The result of this cross table shows that the number of female students is a little bit higher than the male students in case of using Facebook for educational purpose, but the number is not noteworthy.

Who is more educated in your family * Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing Cross tabulation

Families' educational status	Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing?		
	Yes	No	Total

	Father	68	9	77
	Mother	21	0	21
	Brother	44	3	47
	Sister	27	10	37
	You	117	24	141
Total		277	46	323

Table 6: Relation between parents' education and Students' use of Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing

The cross table is about the family educational background and the use of English for developing writing. The students where father is the most educated person in the family, there use Facebook for educational purpose is 68 among 77 the percentage is 88% and where mother is the most educated there the percentage is 100%. If the brother is the most educated person there the percentage is 93%, while sister, there is 72%.

Findings 6: The statistic of the table shows that the parents' education level has a little impact on the students' use of Facebook for educational purpose. If the mother is educated the children are intend to use Facebook for educational purpose more than others. The families where sister is more educated they are less interested in using Facebook for education than the families where brothers are the highest educated person in the family. This could be concluded by saying that, an educated brother is more inspiring than an educated sister.

Collaboratively the major findings of the research are:

Practicing English writing skills based on the students' level of education and gender:

1. The students were selected from the boys and girls colleges to examine the effect of Facebook in improving their writing skills. There is no different between girls' and boys' use of Facebook in improving their writing skills.
2. Among the almost equal number of the education level from Honours' 1st year to Honours' 4th year, it shows that the Honours' 2nd years students are a little bit less interested in using Facebook for educational purposes.

Influence of family education specially parents' education in using English for developing English language writing excellence:

3. Mothers' education has a significant influence in childrens' use of English in Facebook for improving the writing skills. The data shows that if the mother is the mostly educated person in the family, the children are intended to use Facebook for educational purpose, thought the number of fathers education and the number of mothers education are not same but the response in mothers case is higher than the fathers case further researches can be done on this point.

Motivations behind using English in Facebook for enhancing writing skills:

4. The popular reason behind students' use of Facebook for improving their English writing is to make new foreign friend, this could be an impact of their interest to know about the outer world beside their own country (Biswas, 2022).

5. Students often use English during using Facebook as English is easy to type than Bengali alphabet. These findings agree with a study of Biswas (2022).
6. Some students use Facebook for improving their English writing skills so that they can cut a good mark in the exam. And this tendency is higher among comparative senior levels like 3rd and 4th year and the reason behind it could be they are more serious about their career as they are about to finish their education and getting ready to join the job competition. The things motivated the students are their improvement are in certain areas like grammar, vocabulary and creativity.

Challenges in practicing English writing in Facebook:

7. The challenges faced by the students are the lack of vocabulary, inconsistent peer feedback. The students face problem with syntax as the sentence structure of Bengali and English is different as in English it is Subject+Verb+Object but in Bengali it is Subject+Object+Verb (Islam F. S., 2018).

Recommendation:

According to the students faced problem they suggest some recommendations. The recommendations are:

1. The students' English vocabulary must be enriched (Islam F. S., 2018).
2. Peer review must be formative and consistent.
3. Students should not use Facebook only for entertainment, rather they should use purposefully. They must join the English content more and more for developing their writing.
4. They have to develop their level of confident in using English while dealing with their foreign friends with a view to develop their writing skills.
5. The language teachers can encourage the students to use standard language in any writing in Facebook as the frequent use of standard-English is one of the best ways to improve English writing (Islam F. S., Facebook and Students' Sub-Standard English: A Context of Bangladesh., 2018).

Limitations: This study is based on only two government colleges of Dhaka city under seven affiliated colleges of Dhaka University. The samples are from English disciplines only. It may not be the best representative sample size for the whole population. Future researcher can include the students from all disciplines and from all over the countries.

All over the world the social media are used to develop the student English language skills including writing and reading via chatting and game, status. In Bangladesh the students are not yet that much familiar with this learning. Again, the social or traditional teaching does not allow this use as an accepted method .in contrast to Bangladesh different countries of the world like Malaysia, Thailand, Turkey are using Facebook to develop the students' English language skill in various way as discussed in the methodology. Bangladesh can follow their example in larger scale. Yet further study is required for it. As the students spent a huge time in Facebook, it could be a useful tool in increasing writing skill among the students of English department. What they need it just a proper supervision and self-motivation. They should be determined to utilize the technology to develop their skill whether it is writing or reading or cognitive power. They can make a Facebook group to discuss and to check their writing in supervision of an instructor or teacher. This study's limitation is that data was collected from only two colleges. This recommendation of the participants cannot be generalized. Future researcher can increase the sample size to generalize the findings. It could be done in quantitative data an10. **Conclusions:** All over the world the social media are used to develop the student English language skills including writing and reading via chatting and game, status. In Bangladesh the students are not yet that much familiar with this learning. Again, the social or traditional teaching does not allow this use as an accepted method .in contrast to Bangladesh different countries of the world like Malaysia, Thailand, Turkey are using Facebook to develop the students' English language skill in various way as discussed in the methodology. Bangladesh can follow their example in larger scale. However, further research can be performed to explore the other aspects of Facebook as

an educational tool based on a wider area. Yet further study is required for it. As the students spent a huge time in Facebook, it could be a useful tool in increasing writing skill among the students of English department (Klimova, 2019). What they need it just a proper supervision and self-motivation. They should be determined to utilize the technology to develop their skill whether it is writing or reading or cognitive power. They can make a Facebook group to discuss and to check their writing in supervision of an instructor or teacher (Alam, Facebook as a Formal Instructional Environment in Facilitating L2 Writing: Impacts and Challenges., 2019). This study's limitation is that data was collected from only two colleges. This recommendation of the participants cannot be generalized. Future researcher can increase the sample size to generalize the findings. It could be done in quantitative data analysis.

Acknowledgement: I am privileged to accept my gratitude to the students of English department of Dhaka College from Honours 1st year to 4th year, who helped the me to collect data by providing their information. I am also grateful to the students of Eden College English Department students for responding my questionnaire.

Works Cited

- AbuSa'aleek, A. O. (2015). STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN THE FACEBOOK CONTEXT. *Teaching English with Technology*, 4, 60-75.
- Alam, M. Z. (2019). Facebook as a Formal Instructional Environment in Facilitating L2 Writing: Impacts and Challenges. *International Journal of Language Education*, 3(2), 41-48.
- Alam, M. Z. (2019). Facebook as a Formal Instructional Environment in Facilitating L2 Writing: Impacts and Challenges. *International Journal of Language Education*, 3(2), 41-48.
- Arafat, S. M. (2020). History of English Teaching in Bangladesh: From inception to present practice. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(5), 50-56.
- Biswas, M. (2022). English as a Status Marker on Facebook:: The Case of Bangladeshi University Students. *Crossings. A Journal of English Studies*, 13(1), 23-35.
- Chowdhury, A. I. (2021). Impact of Social Networking Sites on Students' Learning English Language at Tertiary Level in Bangladesh. *Studies in ELT and Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 104-115.
- Faryadi, Q. (2017). Effectiveness of Facebook in English language learning: A Case Study. Online Submission.
- Güvendir, E. &. (2015). The effect of a Facebook game that requires English vocabulary knowledge on students' English vocabulary development. *Journal of Educational Sciences Research*, 5(1), 41-55.
- Ibrahim, M. G. (2013). The Effect of Using Facebook on Improving Students' Writing Skills in English.
- Islam, F. S. (2018). Facebook and Students' Sub-Standard English: A Context of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Language Education*, 2(1), 14-21.
- Islam, F. S. (2018). Facebook and Students' Sub-Standard English: A Context of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Language Education*, 2(1), 14-21.
- Islam, N. N. (2016). Using Facebook in and outside of classroom for language education in rural areas of Bangladesh: Prospects and challenges. *Governance and Development*, 157.
- Jassim, L. &. (2019). Effective use of Facebook in improving English communication skills: Conceptual paper. *Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences*, 46(2).
- Kabilan, M. K. (2016). Enhancing students' vocabulary knowledge using the Facebook environment. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 5(2), 2017-230.

- Kasuma, S. A. (2017). Four characteristics of Facebook activities for English language learning: A study of Malaysian university students' needs and preferences. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 8(3), 155-177.
- Kasuma, S. A. (2017). Using Facebook for English Language Learning: the differences among gender and ethnicity. *Journal of Nusantara Studies (JONUS)*, 2(1), 177-193.
- Klimova, B. &. (2019). Cognitive and applied linguistics aspects of using social media: the impact of the use of Facebook on developing writing skills in learning English as a foreign language. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 10(1), 110-118.
- Rahman, M. M. (2018). The Chaotic English Language Policy and Planning in Bangladesh: Areas of Apprehension. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 26(2).
- S. Patmanthara, D. F. (2019). Social Media as a Learning Media: A Comparative Analysis of Youtube, WhatsApp, Facebook and Instagram Utilization. *International Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Information Engineering (ICEEIE)*, (pp. 183-186). Denpasar, Indonesia, 2019: 10.1109/ICEEIE47180.2019.8981441.
- Salameh, Z. (2017). Attitudes towards Facebook and the use of knowledge and skills among students in the English Department at the University of Hail. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(8), 1-6.
- Sayed, A. H. (2020). Facebook addiction associated with internet activity, depression and behavioral factors among university students of Bangladesh: A cross-sectional study. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 118.
- Srirat, K. (2014). Using Facebook group to facilitate teaching English for everyday communication. *WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings*.
- Sufian, M. A. (2015). Facebook Could Motivate EFL Learners to Develop Genre Based Writing Skills:: A Study on Bangladeshi Undergraduate Learners' Emersion in Free Writing Space. *Crossings: A Journal of English Studies*, 6(2), 146-151.

Appendix 1 Questionnaire:

Dear students,

This is an article survey to assess the effectiveness of Facebook in improving writing skills of the students of English department. The participants' identity would not be disclosed and ethical consideration would be strictly performed during this study. Thank you.

Wishes,

Mst. Ummehani Akter
Lecturer, Dhaka College, Dhaka
Email: ummehaniedu37@gmail.com

Section 1:

1. Name of your institution (choose one)
 - a. Dhaka College
 - b. Eden College
2. Education Level
 - a. Honours 1st Year
 - b. Honours 2nd Year
 - c. Honours 1st Year
 - d. Honours 1st Year
3. Where are you from?
 - a. Town
 - b. Suburban
 - c. Town
4. Write the name of your district: _____ .
5. What is the highest level of education your parents have completed?
 - a. SSC
 - b. HSC
 - c. BA
 - d. MA
 - e. PhD
 - f. Others
6. Who is the most educated in your family?
 - a. Father
 - b. Mother
 - c. Brother
 - d. Sister
 - e. You

Section 2: Facebook related questions.

7. When did you create your Facebook account?
 - a. Before SSC
 - b. During SSC
 - c. During HSC
 - d. After HSC
 - e. Other

8. How often do you use Facebook?
 - a. Daily
 - b. Weekly
 - c. Monthly
 - d. Rarely
 - e. Never
9. How many hours do you spend on Facebook?
 - a. Less than 1 hour
 - b. 1-2 hours
 - c. 2-3 hours
 - d. More than 3 hours

Section 3: Use of Facebook for educational purposes focusing on English writing development:

10. Do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English Writing development?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
11. If yes, how often do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on English writing development?
 - a. Daily
 - b. Weekly
 - c. Monthly
 - d. Rarely
12. How many hours do you use Facebook for educational purpose focusing on writing?
 - a. 1-1.30 hour
 - b. 2 hour
 - c. 1 hour to 30 minute
 - d. Less than 30 minute
13. What motivates you to use English in Facebook? (Refer all those apply)
 - a. Using English increases my prestige
 - b. It helps me making new friends
 - c. It helps me obtaining good marks in exam by increasing my writing skills
 - d. Using English helps me make more friends from abroad
 - e. Others
14. Have you participated in any English writing activities or groups on Facebook?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
15. If yes, what kind of activities or group? (Refer all those apply)
 - a. Writing groups
 - b. English language learning pages
 - c. Writing challenges
 - d. Peer review and feedback
 - e. Others
16. Do you believe that participating in these activities or groups has improved your English writing skills?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

17. How has Facebook helped you to improve your English writing? (Select all that apply)

- a. Increased practice opportunities
- b. Access to resources and materials
- c. Feedback from peers and experts
- d. Exposure to different writing styles
- e. Others

18. Which specific areas of your English writing have been improved through the use of Facebook? (Select all that apply)

- a. Grammar
- b. Vocabulary
- c. Sentence structure
- d. Coherence and cohesion
- e. Creativity and originality
- f. Others

Section 4: Challenges and recommendation

19. What challenges have you faced when using Facebook for improving English writing? (Select all that apply)

- a. Destruction from non-educational content
- b. Lack of structural learning material
- c. Inconsistent feedback
- d. Privacy concern
- e. Lack of vocabulary
- f. Lack of confidence

20. How satisfied are you with the use of Facebook as a tool for improving your English writing skills?

- a. Very satisfied
- b. Satisfied
- c. Neutral
- d. Dissatisfied
- e. Very Dissatisfied

21. Would you recommend using Facebook for improving English writing to others?

- a. Yes
- b. No

22. Please provide any additional comments or suggestions on using Facebook for improving English writing:
